

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of studying competition in the market of medical services is because competition stimulates medical institutions to improve the quality of services provided; promotes competition for patients, which can lead to lower prices for medical services; stimulates introduction of innovations (new methods of treatment, digital technologies) to stand out from competitors; encourages institutions to listen to their patients and take into account their needs. At the same time, it seems necessary to develop effective state regulatory measures that will promote a healthy competitive environment and protect the interests of consumers.

The study of competition in the medical services market is essential not only from the point of view of economic efficiency but also of ensuring a high level of health care and satisfaction of the population.

Literature review

The state creates the rules of the game in the medical services market and actively regulates balanced access, quality, and innovation in health care.

A. Mwachofi and A. F. Al-Assaf write that government intervention would be unnecessary if market mechanisms effectively allocated resources in health care. As such, government involvement in health care is often necessary [1]. S. Dougherty et al. found that under moderate decentralization, public expenditure on health care is lower and life expectancy is higher compared to more centralized systems; however, in highly decentralized systems, public spending is higher and life expectancy is lower [2].

K. H. Lee et al. studied the characteristics of competition among healthcare providers introducing high-tech medical equipment in South Korea. The authors found that faced with fierce competition, Korean hospitals focused on non-medical conveniences for patients rather than on introducing new medical technologies or improving inpatient care [3].

The ideal approach to organizing medical services combines elements of both competition and cooperation. Competition can motivate institutions to improve quality and reduce prices, while cooperation can enhance the availability and integration of health services. To ensure the most efficient operation of the health care system, a balance between these two dynamics is essential, ultimately leading to better health outcomes for the population.

H. Alderwick writes that cooperation between local healthcare and non-medical organizations can theoretically improve public health [4].

El Mokrini et al. write that the consumption of pharmaceuticals in hospitals and health centers is characterized by demand uncertainty, especially during unusual events such as pandemics and other crises.

T. Shakeel et al. explore the possibilities and feasibility of collaborating with hospitals and other health centers by pooling supplies. Costs vary considerably and depend on the type of products, population density of the region, per capita income, and level of urbanization [5].

In both competition and cooperation between healthcare organizations, patient satisfaction with the quality of care is a key component of the healthcare system.

The experience of the Netherlands is interesting, where health insurers are interested in involving citizens in the procurement of services in order to contract for health services that are important to people. Brito Fernandes et al. identified strategies health insurers use to engage citizens, but low levels of trust in health insurers hinder transition from simple healthcare financing to value-based, people-centered health services [6].

Today, health insurance covers almost 100% of China's population. China provides its population with social safety nets that protect people from impoverishment due to the need to incur high healthcare costs. W. C. Yip points out that provision of health care in China is still difficult due to inefficiency, poor quality of services, and shortage and uneven distribution of skilled labor [7].

According to Y. Egli et al, Switzerland has a number of measures aimed to control the cost of medicines, yet they are not effective enough. The authors found that generics, market size and physician specialization are associated with lower costs, while drugs requiring a physician's prescription, patient age, gender and comorbidities increase costs [8].

Information technology significantly improves the quality of health care by increasing the accessibility, efficiency and safety of health care services.

Y. K. Patrick et al. write that information technology in providing medical services is an important tool in supporting clinical decision-making [9].

According to T. Shakeel et al, Internet of Things technology (IoMT) in health care contributes to improving patient safety, reducing prices for medical services, and increasing the number of available medical services [10].

A. B. Rao et al. analyze the market basket in the healthcare industry. The authors use the Apriori algorithm to search for the most frequent diseases in a particular region in order to prevent these diseases [11].

J. P. Jansen believes that network meta-analysis has significant advantages for selecting the best treatment option [12].

Public reporting on the quality of medical care is also an important tool for increasing the responsibility and efficiency of the health care system.

According to A. Han et al., public reporting is considered effective in reducing health care costs due to the mitigation of information asymmetry in the market. However, despite the widespread advocacy of healthcare transparency, the effectiveness of public reporting has not yet been sufficiently studied [13].

According to C. Strumann et al., public reporting on the quality of medical care is designed to direct patients to the provider with the highest quality and to stimulate fair competition on quality. The authors found a homogeneous positive effect of competition on quality of care. This effect is mainly driven by the response of nonprofit hospitals that offer a narrow range of services and private for-profit hospitals with a medium range of services [14].

Thus, we found that there is a dearth of systematic and empirical studies showing how competition affects the quality and accessibility of health care services.

Competition can affect not only economic indicators but also intangible aspects such as patient satisfaction and professionalism of health care providers. It is necessary to develop criteria and methods for assessing the effectiveness of the functioning of the health care system when introducing competitive mechanisms.

The article aims to analyze the impact of competition in the service market on patient satisfaction with the quality of medical care.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were studies published in peer-reviewed journals Sultan Qaboos University medical journal, The European Journal of Health Economics, BMC Health Services Research, Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management, BMC Public Health and other publications that provide relevant data and theoretical foundations for analyzing competition in healthcare.

The coefficient of satisfaction with the quality of health care services was used as a method.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The study of population satisfaction with health services

Beginning in 2016, the authors analyzed the level of competition in the markets of social services, including medical services. As part of this analysis, the satisfaction coefficient of the price – quality ratio, first described in [15] and allowing to establish what exactly (price or quality) the consumer is dissatisfied with, was proposed. The authors assume that due to the peculiarities of the market of medical services, the consumer is ready to pay for the quality of medical care. Therefore, the target benchmark is the outstripping growth of satisfaction with quality compared to satisfaction with price. The coefficient is calculated according to the formula:

$$K_{pq} = U_p / U_q \quad (1)$$

where

U_p is balance of customer satisfaction with the price of services (goods, works);

U_q is balance of customer satisfaction with the quality of services (goods, works).

The indicators U_p and U_q represent the excess of the share of satisfied consumers over the share of dissatisfied consumers. For example, if the share of satisfied consumers amounts to 53%, and dissatisfied ones to 27%, the balance is in favor of the satisfied and is 26%, therefore, $U_q = 26$.

The possible values of the coefficient are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Ranges of values of the coefficient of satisfaction

Value range of K_{pq}	Value range of U_p	Value range of U_q	Characterization of the market situation
$K_{pq} < 0$	$U_p > 0$ at $U_q < 0$ or $U_p < 0$ at $U_q > 0$	$U_q > 0$ at $U_p < 0$ or $U_q < 0$ at $U_p > 0$	The consumer is dissatisfied with one of the components of the price – quality ratio (price or quality). The more modulo the value of K_{pq} , the higher the dissatisfaction with the level of price versus quality.
$K_{pq} > 0$	$U_p > 0$	$U_q > 0$	Satisfaction with both components is observed in the market. The larger the value of the coefficient, the more consumers are satisfied with price level versus quality satisfaction
$K_{pq} > 0$	$U_p < 0$	$U_q < 0$	Dissatisfaction with both components prevails in the market. The larger the coefficient, the greater the extent to which consumers are dissatisfied with the price level relative to their dissatisfaction with quality.
$K_{pq} = 0$ (or K_{pq} tending to infinity)	$U_p = 0$ at $U_p < 0$ or $U_p > 0$	$U_q = 0$ at $U_p < 0$ or $U_p > 0$	The balance of satisfaction with one of the components is zero. In other words, the proportions of consumers satisfied and dissatisfied with one of the components of expression (1) are equal. This is a boundary condition when consumer satisfaction can change to dissatisfaction and vice versa.

Satisfaction with both components is observed in the market. The larger the value of the coefficient, the more consumers are satisfied with price level versus quality satisfaction

Dissatisfaction with both components prevails in the market. The larger the coefficient, the greater the extent to which consumers are dissatisfied with the price level relative to their dissatisfaction with quality.

The balance of satisfaction with one of the components is zero. In other words, the proportions of consumers satisfied and dissatisfied with one of the components of expression (1) are equal. This is a boundary condition when consumer satisfaction can change to dissatisfaction and vice versa.

Within the framework of approbation of the proposed coefficient, the above indicators were calculated for several regions of Russia. The choice of RF subjects was conditioned by the need to see the results of surveys and generalized indicators in different parts of the country, so the authors refused to use a sample of only the regions of the Central Federal District.

The variants of the ratio of the indicators U_p and U_q reflect different states of consumer satisfaction, which can be divided into four segments:

- I) the consumer is satisfied with both price and quality;
- II) the consumer is satisfied with neither price nor quality;
- III) the consumer is satisfied with the price but not quality;
- IV) the consumer is satisfied with the quality but not price.

In Samara, Ryazan, and Smolensk Oblasts, dissatisfaction with both parameters is observed (segment III). In Smolensk Oblast, the level of dissatisfaction is the same for both price and quality (see Table 2), while in Ryazan Oblast, the balance of dissatisfaction with price is 2.25 times higher than dissatisfaction with quality. In Moscow Oblast, (segment IV) dissatisfaction with the price of medical services with satisfaction with quality is observed. Therefore, the coefficient K_{pq} has a negative value. In other regions, the balance of satisfaction is positive and shows a slight excess in quality.

Table 2

Indicators of satisfaction with price and quality of medical services in Russian regions

Indicators	Samara Oblast	Moscow Oblast	Kemerovo Oblast	Ryazan Oblast	Voronezh Oblast	Smolensk Oblast
Share of satisfied respondents from the total number of respondents, %						
price level	31.6	37	55.6	33	72.2	22
quality	39.5	66	58.6	36	77.8	20
Share of dissatisfied respondents from the total number of respondents, %						
price level	68,4	58	42,6	51	27,8	63
quality	60.5	31	39.3	44	22.2	61
U_p	-36.8	-21	13	-18	44.4	-41
U_q	-21	35	19.3	-8	55.6	-41
K_{pq}	1.75	-0.6	0.67	2.25	0.8	1

The proposed coefficient can be used not only to analyze the situation in the market of medical services but also to subsequently monitor of the effectiveness of the health system model.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There are a number of activities that contribute to improving the quality of health services among the population.

Today, the use of information technologies is relevant, in particular, introduction of electronic medical records which allows health workers to share information about patients more effectively, which contributes to more accurate diagnosis and treatment.

It is important to expand access to health services through remote consultations, and to use mobile applications for real-time health monitoring.

There is a need for patient-centeredness, i.e. creating systems that allow patients to provide feedback and ratings on services provided, with further analysis for quality improvement.

Publication of information on the quality of medical services to create a transparent environment will promote competition between institutions. Systems for assessing the quality of medical services with the possibility of comparison between different institutions are necessary.

Thus, the prospects for improving the quality of medical services among the population are in the context of integration of new technologies, orientation to the needs of patients and continuous professional development of medical staff.

REFERENCES

1. Mwachofi, A., & Al-Assaf, A. F. (2011). Health care market deviations from the ideal market. *Sultan Qaboos University medical journal*, 11(3), 328–337.
2. Dougherty, S., Lorenzoni, L., Marino, A. et al. (2022). The impact of decentralisation on the performance of health care systems: a non-linear relationship. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 23, 705–715.
3. Lee, K. H., Lim, S. & Moon, J. (2022). The Link Between Hospital Competition and Hospital Behaviors in Korea: Competitive Interorganizational Relations. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 23 (Suppl 1), 1–14.
4. Alderwick, H., Hutchings, A., Briggs, A., et al. (2021). The impacts of collaboration between local health care and non-health care organizations and factors shaping how they work: a systematic review of reviews. *BMC Public Health*, 21, 753.
5. El Mokrini, A., Aouam, T. & Kafa, N. (2023). A tailored aggregation strategy for inventory pooling in healthcare: evidence from an emerging market. *Operations Management*

- Research*, 16, 209–226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-022-00302-7>
6. Brito Fernandes, Y., Bos, V., Klazinga, N. et al. (2022). Citizen engagement in healthcare procurement decision-making by healthcare insurers: recent experiences in the Netherlands. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 20, 137. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-022-00939-7>
 7. Yip, W. C., Hsiao, W. C., Chen, W., Hu, S., Ma, J., & Maynard, A. (2012). Early appraisal of China's huge and complex healthcare reforms. *Lancet (London, England)*, 379(9818), 833–842. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(11\)61880-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(11)61880-1)
 8. Egli, Y., Decollogny, A., Piaget-Rossel, R. et al. (2022). Determinants of drug expenditure in the Swiss healthcare market in 2006. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22, 875. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08212-x>
 9. Patrick Y.K. Chau, Paul Jen-Hwa Hu. (2002). Investigating healthcare professionals' decisions to accept telemedicine technology: an empirical test of competing theories. *Information & Management*, 39 (4), 297-311.
 10. Shakeel, T., Habib, S., Boulila, W. et al. (2022). A survey on COVID-19 impact in the healthcare domain: worldwide market implementation, applications, security and privacy issues, challenges and future prospects. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 9, 1027–1058. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40747-022-00767-w>
 11. Rao, A.B., Kiran, J.S. & G, P. (2023). Application of market–basket analysis on healthcare. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, 14 (Suppl 4), 924–929. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13198-021-01298-2>
 12. Jeroen P. Jansen, Rachael Fleurence, Beth Devine, Robbin Itzler, Annabel Barrett, Neil Hawkins, Karen Lee, Cornelis Boersma, Lieven Annemans, Joseph C. Cappelleri. (2011). Interpreting Indirect Treatment Comparisons and Network Meta-Analysis for Health-Care Decision Making: Report of the ISPOR Task Force on Indirect Treatment Comparisons Good Research Practices: Part 1. *Value in Health*, 14 (4), 417–428.
 13. Han, A., Lee, KH. & Park, J. (2022). The impact of price transparency and competition on hospital costs: research on all-payer claims databases. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22, 1321.
 14. Strumann, C., Geissler, A., Busse, R. et al. (2022). Can competition improve hospital quality of care? A difference-in-differences approach to evaluate the effect of increasing quality transparency on hospital quality. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 23, 1229–1242.
 15. Gorbova O.Yu., Perfiliev S.V. (2021). Evaluation of consumer satisfaction with the ratio “price-quality” on commodity markets. *Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 134 (9), 662–671.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Olga Yu. Gorbova (Russia, Ryazan) – Associate Professor, Cand. Sci. (Econ.), Dean of the Faculty of Engineering and Economics. Ryazan State Radio Engineering University. E-mail: odina-olga@yandex.ru

Sergey V. Perfiliev (Russia, Ryazan) – Professor, Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Head of the Department of State, Municipal and Corporate Governance. Ryazan State Radio Engineering University. E-mail: perfilev.c.v@rsreu.ru

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2022/03/01/gorbova/>

Received: Dec 16, 2021 | **Accepted:** Feb 6, 2022 | **Published:** Mar 1, 2022

Editor: Tamara K. Rostovskaya, Russian State Social University, RUSSIA

Copyright: © 2022 Gorbova, O. Yu., Perfiliev, S. V. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.